

THE STYLISTIC ROLE AND ARTISTIC FUNCTION OF OXYMORON UNITS

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Annotation: *This article examines the stylistic and artistic function of oxymoron units in literature and linguistics. As a rhetorical device, oxymorons enhance expressiveness and deepen meaning. The study explores their linguistic role, use in literary texts, and translation challenges. Through examples from Uzbek and English literature, it indicates their ability to convey irony, paradox, and emotion, emphasizing their significance in both classical and modern works.*

Keywords: *oxymoron, stylistics, linguistics, literary devices, translation, expressiveness, contrast, paradox.*

Kirish. An oxymoron is a combination of words or phrases with opposite meanings, serving to enhance the expressiveness of literary speech and to convey the author's intention more deeply. This stylistic device is widely used in literature, journalism, and everyday speech.

According to researchers, an oxymoron is a specific form of antithesis where “completely opposite words are combined to create a new meaning” (Lapasov, 2003). Therefore, the oxymoron is considered one of the means of expressing contrast between linguistic units. Some sources highlight that “the opposing pair components involved in forming this type of contrast ensure structural symmetry in contrast as a specific structural-semantic feature” (Axmanova, 1969).

Literary scholars underscore the significance of oxymoron as a stylistic device in artistic works. Some researchers state that “the method of depicting a person's character, the qualities and properties of objects and phenomena by contrasting them with one another” serves as an essential stylistic tool (Khotamov & Sarimsoqov, 1979). Furthermore, according to other sources, “An oxymoron appears as a phrase consisting of two words, where the contextual meaning emerges while each word retains its individual meaning” (Karimov, 1994).

From a stylistic perspective, the oxymoron holds a distinct place. Some stylistic studies describe it as “a key unit based on the incompatibility of the stylistic coloring of words in expression, despite their interrelation according to general linguistic norms” (Kojina, 2003). Additionally, researchers argue that “the primary function of an oxymoron is to express the author's personal attitude toward the depicted

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phenomenon” (Kukharenko, 1979). This paper analyzes the stylistic role and artistic function of oxymoron units.

In linguistics, the oxymoron is seen as a combination of antonymic words or concepts. As a stylistic device, it imparts irony, expressiveness, or a philosophical tone to the text. The primary features of oxymoron units include creating a new semantic layer by merging contradictory concepts, expanding the expressive potential of language and speech, enhancing the semantic depth of a text.

According to Axmanova (1969), the oxymoron is one of the means of expressing contrast between linguistic units. She states that “the opposing pair components involved in forming this type of contrast ensure structural symmetry in contrast as a specific structural-semantic feature.” Such linguistic units are stylistically rich and enhance the expressiveness of a text.

In literary texts, oxymorons serve the author’s aesthetic purpose. Writers use them to express characters’ emotions, highlight contradictory situations, or add vividness to the text. For example, in Uzbek literature, Abdulla Qodiriy’s works contain oxymorons. In the novel *O‘tkan kunlar*, phrases like “shirin azob” (sweet torment) and “ziddiyatli do‘stlik” (contradictory friendship) reflect the complex inner experiences of the characters.

In English literature, William Shakespeare’s *Romeo and Juliet* employs numerous oxymorons to convey the meaning of the play. For instance, expressions like “*o loving hate*” and “*cold fire*” intensify the contrast between love and enmity. Shakespeare uses this technique to depict the complexity of human emotions.

The translation of oxymorons is also a significant issue in linguistics. Each language has its own semantic and stylistic rules, which can create difficulties in translating oxymorons. For instance, the English word “*bittersweet*” is a commonly used oxymoron, which can be translated into Uzbek as “*shirin iztirob*” (sweet sorrow) or “*achchiq baxt*” (bitter happiness).

Karimov (1994) states that an oxymoron “appears as a phrase consisting of two words, where the contextual meaning emerges while each word retains its individual meaning.” This demonstrates that finding an exact translation equivalent is not always straightforward.

Oxymoron units serve as a means of carrying deep meaning in literary texts, adding expressiveness, irony, and a philosophical approach. While their stylistic function remains similar across languages, translation may pose some challenges. This paper has examined the stylistic and artistic significance of oxymorons and discussed their role in translation.

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